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THE SCENCE OF HUMAN PERFECTION IN NIZAMI GANJAVI CREATIVITY

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Abstract

One of the greatest mysteries of ancient Eastern culture is meditation. The main purpose of the meditation, that is directly related to the soul and body, to deliver a person to a perfect condition by bringing him to his true nature. In the works of Eastern classic Nizami Ganjavi there is also manifested deep philosophical meditation. In his works, the poet concludes that growing up a perfect person was not an easy task. In this complex and lengthy process everyone must believe in their own strength, study the nature, society and environment carefully and deeply, must be able to look at life with an open eye. In a word, the human can become perfect by regular evolution. Such moments are reflected in almost all works of Nizami. In the article, the characters rising up to the perfection by meditation are analyzed.

Keywords: Khamsa, Nizami, meditation, human, love, perfection

INTRODUCTION

The actuality of the subject. Although the N. Ganjavi creativity has been analyzed in many research works in various directions, it is comprehensive and rich enough to allow approaches from new perspectives and commentaries in modern society standards. First of all, the Nizami art is human and a school for humanity. Therefore, the Nizami creativity remains relevant for each period.

Research methodology. In the research, there were used descriptive, historical-comparative methods. The article examines the images of Nizami Ganjavi passing through the stages of spiritual development.

Sources of research. The researches on Nizami creativity, as well as his works, are the main source of the research. The articles of A. Alizade, N. Gurbanov, N. Mammadli, I. Gojayev and other authors were used as a source.

I. THE MEDITATION IN EASTERN CULTURE

Nizami Ganjavi (real name-Ilyas Yusif oglu) was born in was born in 1141 in Ganja, one of the ancient cultural centres of Azerbaijan and the capital of the Azerbaijani Atabey's state. Nizami also became closely acquainted with the oral and written literature of the Near East. "Nizami Ganjavi, who began by writing lyrics in short forms – gasida, gazal, rubai, soon compiled an anthology, Divan, and gained fame as a favourite and esteemed poet not only in the Near and Middle East, but also on distant shores" (Kerimli, 2011). Nizami is not only a poet, but also a scientist, a perfect researcher, a large-scale historian, a linguist, who knows several foreign languages, a moral scholar, whose advices and recommendations have not become obsolete for eight centuries and are more important for today's generation. (Alizade, 2001)

The greatest poet, wise philosopher Nizami Ganjavi has reached the highest peak of human thinking with his creativity. This is such a peak that in order to conquer it, the writer must develop spiritually. The spiritual uplift of the images in the work of Nizami and

their passage of a mystical path serve the perfection of society. The "chosen" characters in the work of Nizami meditate for spiritual change and reach perfection. Sometimes this meditation is confidential, invisible, "hidden" under a mysterious shell and symbolized.

The meditation is a technique of spiritual purification practiced in many different cultures and religions, and as an ancient style it manifests itself in various religions and beliefs.

The meditation is a word derived from the Latin "meditatio", which means to consider and think about something. In other words, the meditation is remembered as a thinking in terms of the deep thought (basically "not to think intellectually") and themysticism. In a word, it is a deep thought without thinking about anything.

In Eastern culture, the meditation is considered as an ancient and a mind-opening technique. The main development direction of the meditation is related to Indian Yoga and Buddhism. The mysticism is not only a widespread esoteric religious and philosophical movement in Islam, but also is a tuition aimed at the correction of the spiritual world of human. The elements associated with mysticism, that forms the basis of the Nizami creativity, are connected with human perfection.

II. THE MEDITATION OF THE SPIRITUALLY DEVELOPING IMAGES

In the poem "The seven beauties" Nizami Ganjavi guides his protagonist to the perfection in various ways. The main character of the work, Bahram, steps on the four-stage perfection path of the Sufism – "Shariat-Sect-Erudition-Reality, and on the seven-stage model of the Tarikat (sect). Nizami Ganjavi, who also appealed to the parallel world models of that period in the perfection of the main character, created an original hero. Throughout the poem, Bahram Gur, goes through a stage of development through the meditation, eventually reaching perfection. We can see this perfection in the background of the stages Fena and Bega:

*Bahram Gur while hunting in the steppes
A fluffy passed by him*

*King knew that he was invited to the heaven
Immediately fell in love with such an invitation
(The Seven beauties, 2004,286).*

It is also clear from these hemistiches given in the last chapter of the poem that Bahram, who followed the fluffy and entered the cave on horseback with love of paradise and the desire to reunite with God, disappeared there. No matter how hard they looked for him, they could not find. We can also see this episode in surah al-Kahf of the Holy Quran. According to the legend in thi surah, youth that believe in monotheism, hide in cave together to escape from the tyranny and persecution of idolater ruler. They came out of this cave 309 years later. When youth saw that the world, times and the period had change, they asked God to put them to sleep forever again and each of them disappears, leaning on a rock. Bahram Gur went through a long mystical way until his disappearance in the cave. Bahram Gur hides in the rooms of girls from seven countries, changes up with their stories and rises to the highest peak.

The first of the seven stories told by girls in the poem is about black and the last is about white color.

It is no fortuitous that the first color of the Bahram's development point in the way of upbringing with seven stories is black, and the color of the seventh layer of his spiritual evolution is white. On the seven-step sect path between black and white, Bahram's passionate love is replaced by the divine love. The first story is told in a black room by an Indian princess and is about black dressed ones. The main idea of this story is to fight against passion and to kill lust. Note that, in Indian philosophy the color of the root chakra called Muladhara is dark red and it is associated with genitals. In the yellow room the Greek princess tells Bahram a story about an Iraqi king who takes a maid, not a wife. In an Indian philosophy the color of the second chakra is orange, and the pathology of this chakra reveals bad qualities such as envy and falsity. In the second tale in "The seven beauties", the king's maids are liars and hypocrites. Suleiman Shakh and Bilgeys are punished with a disabled child for lying. This story criticizes such qualities as hypocrisy, cunning and disloyalty. The third story told to Bahram in the green dome is about Bishr, who overcame the lust and renounced adultery. According to the idea of the story, if a person fights with his inner passion and overcomes his lust, he will be rewarded by God. The fourth tale narrated to Bahram by the Slavic princess is about a girl who tests people who want to marry her. In the end, one man overcomes all trials and gets married to her. The fifth tale told to Bahrama is about Mahan, a merchant who suffered because of his greedlines.the idea of the sixth tale is about the victory of the Good over the Evil. At the beginning of the story, Evil's does badness against his friend Good. But the Good leads to the destruction of the Evil, with its kindness and purity. The seventh tale narrated to Bahram by Iranian princess is about the hermit, who succumbed to his lust and then returned to the path of God. If we look at the content of the stories, we see that there is followed the process of spiritual improvement of the human. After listening to the stories of the seven beauties, Bahram Gur rises to a certain

level, and after the old shepherd's lesson, Bahram's listening to seven innocent prisoners makes him even more perfect. After all these processes, Bahram disappears.

We see Alexander, the image raised by Nizami Ganjavi to the level of prophecy, as both a conqueror and a philosopher. "The prophecy is the last stage of Alexander's life and his rise as a human being. God's messenger tells Alexander that he has been prophesied. By command of God, he must travel the world and invite people to the love, deter them from the evil path, awake the countries from ignorance, save the world from the actions of the evil forces and invite them to the path of God, awake those who are asleep, and remove the veil from their minds. In this, he must rely not only on his own strength, but also on God's help." (Gojayevev, 2016).

Alexander, during his prophetic journey, asked God for help and miracles. God blessed him with two powers: the light and the darkness are given to Alexander by God's command; so the light will always be in front of him, and the darkness will always be behind him, that he will see everyone, and no one will be able to see him. By the use of this miracle, Alexander shed light on those who followed him, and plunged into darkness those, who fought against him and did not accept God. The second extraordinary power was that Alexander knew the languages of all peoples, and at the same time all nations understood his Greek without translation (Iskendernameh, 2004: 112-113).

So, Alexander added the divine competences to his conquest and philosophical powers, to the qualities of a prophet. On his trip, he takes with him the "Admonitions" given to him by philosophers, in addition to the "The Great Book" ("Sidri-Azam") given to him by God. This includes the admonitions of the Aristotle, Plato and Socrates. Alexander matures on these trips, gaining a deeper understanding of the universe. "By listening to the voice of the benevolent forces in the heart, the mighty ruler, who conquered all lands, witnessed great instructive scenes by shedding blood and demolishing houses, realizes that it is possible to attain eternal glory only by serving the people with good intentions, by standing up for truth and justice, and by proclaiming good deeds". (Gurbanov, 2015,4).

III. THE PEAK OF DIVINE LOVE

In the poem "Leyli and Majnun" written by Nizami Ganjavi on the theme of love, Geys, the protagonist, moves towards perfection through the influence of love throughout the poem. Born with a great love at the beginning, Geys, falls in love with Leila as a teenager. He becomes more and more perfect, cultivates his passion and tastes the wine of great love, with this love. "Majnun is the spiritual condition of Geys, a state that reflects his mental situation, that is, madness of love is a condition that dominates the heart of Geys. In other words, after falling in love Geys become madness and crazy". (Mammadli, 2021).

Geys is kneaded with love, eventually goes to the desert, and begins to live among the animals. The harmony with the nature is the main core of the meditation. So that, Geys integrates with nature. His relatives advise to take him to the Kaaba for healing. When they

turn Majnun around the Ka'bah and pray for him, he asks God for love instead of healing and returns to the desert. The poet connects an image that reaches the peak of love with nature. According to the poet, human is the glory of the universe, and in fact, God created the universe in honor of the human. In the meditation, giving up something you love is also at the forefront when fighting the passion. So, when Majnun meets Leyli he chases her away, somehow rejects her, and gets satisfied with her love, not her body. And that's why at the end of the work, the lovers are reunited with their souls, not their bodies.

The meditation of Majnun also includes fasting, abstaining from meat and other foods. In his dialogue with his uncle Salim Amiri, we can see Majnun's refusal from eat:

"When Salim realized that even his magic powers of persuasion were wasted and that the choicest sweets would only be thrown to the dogs, he asked: 'What do you feed on, then? If you are human, not a demon, you must eat, you unhappy creature. But what? What do you feed on?' 'My heart is "salim" — "sound" — like your name', replied Majnun, 'even if my body has forgotten how to eat. All I can tell you is that I no longer desire food. A few roots and grasses are all I need. But I am not alone here. As you can see, my animals are only too happy to accept your presents. Watching them stills my hunger too" (Leyli and Majnun, 2004:192).

In the poem "Khosrov and Shirin" (Khosrov and Shirin, 2004) we meet the protagonist who turns from pampering to royalty, from royalty to true lover, through the meditation. Although he could not reach the level of Majnun with his love, Khosrov, who managed to make a revolution in his spiritual world, has come a long way. In this poem, love comes to the fore as a main human quality and a basic aesthetic value. In the love of Khosrov and Shirin – lovers, that reunite with more feelings of passion, there are also felt the sparks of divine. Although the harmony of the body and the soul in love is often broken, in the end the spiritual beauty and the reunion come to the fore. The problem of love, which is reflected in the relationship between Khosrov and Shirin, Farhad and Shirin, is also expressed in the form of philosophical statements from the author's point of view. Khosrov's love for Shirin begins up with the feelings of fun and lust. After the "lesson" of Shirin, it becomes a divine, eternal love. The emptiness in Khosrov's inner world is manifested in his attitude towards other women, in his cunning behavior towards his rival Farhad. Khosrov bears himself the punishment for these mistakes. Khosrov's meditation takes place with Shirin's behavior. Thanks to Shirin Khosrov visited his inner world. Although the lovers

are physically reunited in this poem, the eternity occurs with death, and in the end, divine love triumphs. At the end of the poems "Leyli and Majnun", "Khosrov and Shirin" the death of lovers serves to perpetuate their love.

CONCLUSION

In this article we came to the following conclusion:

1. The main characters of the Nizami Ganjavi creativity reach the perfection through the meditation.
2. There are different ways in the development of the main characters.
 - a) The protagonist of Nizami Ganjavi's "The seven beauties" disappears in the cave like a saint through a four-stage, seven-step perfection path.
 - b) Majnun meditates refusing to eat meat, among animals.
 - c) In the poem "Khosrov and Shirin" the protagonist turns from pampering to royalty, from royalty to true lover through meditation.
 - ç) Alexander encounters meditative situations during his prophetic journey.

As can be seen, in all works of Nizami, the protagonist has gone through a meditative path, conquered his desires, perfected himself, and finally refused the blessings of the world.

References

1. Alizade A. (2021) Sciences of the Earth in Nizami poetry <https://www.azerbaijan-news.az/posts/detail/nizami-poetry-in-the-place-science1615668075>
2. Ganjavi Nizami (2004) Khosrov and Shirin. Baku, "Leader Publishing", 392 page.
3. Ganjavi Nizami (2004) Leyli and Majnun. Baku, "Leader Publishing", 288 page.
4. Ganjavi Nizami (2004) The Seven beauties. Baku, "Leader Publishing", 336 page.
5. Ganjavi Nizami. (2004) Iskendernameh. Igbalnameh. Baku, "Leader Publishing" 256 page.
6. Gojayev M. (2016) Iskendernameh. June 20, 2016. <https://kaspi.az/en/201606201040-isgendernameh/pages/config/xml/config.xml>
7. Gurbanov N. (2015). The problem of the perfect man in Nizami Ganjavi creativity. Zaman, 2015, December 2, p.4.
8. Mammadli I. (2021) Majnun's incompatible love with the world from Nizami's pen. January 26, 2021. <https://525.az/news/160857-mecnunun-cahana-sigmayan-asiqliyi-nizami-qeleminde-meqale>
9. Kerimli T. (2011) Nizami - poet for all humanity. <http://www.visions.az/en/news/271/a3e8bd5c/>